

BACKLOG MANAGEMENT DATA

Epic data

We extracted the following variables per epic:

- *acc-criteria*: whether the customer has been consulted to define acceptance criteria for the delivery of an epic.
- *business-goal*: the business goal of an epic. Values include: 'business transformation', 'business continuity' and 'external obligation' (risk or security related).
- *cycle-time*: the sprint duration of teams working on an epic.
- *dev-seniority*: the total number of senior developers working on an epic.
- *env-incidents*: the number of environmental incidents that were active during the development phase of an epic.
- *global-distance*: the maximum Global Distance Metric [84] measured across pair-wise combinations of all teams working on an epic. The locations of teams were derived from the *office address* field.
- *novelty*: whether the *business-goal* field of an epic is set to 'business transformation'.
- *nr-changed-leads*: the number of times the tribe lead of teams changed during the current and previous epic.
- *nr-incidents*: the number of incidents that were active during the development phase of an epic.
- *nr-points*: the total number of story points assigned to an epic.
- *nr-sprints*: the number of sprints assigned to an epic.
- *nr-stories*: the number of stories assigned to an epic.
- *nr-teams*: the number of teams working on an epic.
- *nr-unplanned-stories*: the total number of stories that were added to an epic after the start of its development phase. Unplanned stories are related to bug fixes and incidents at ING.
- *nr-updates*: the number of times the *description* field of an epic was updated before its *actual start date*.
- *out-degree*: the number of outgoing dependencies of an epic on other epics.
- *security-level*: a rating of the criticality of an epic. Values include: 1 (high) - implementation of the epic involves a business-critical system and cannot be shipped without passing required security tests, 2 (low) - implementation of the epic does not involve a critical system and security tests are optional based on resources.
- *state-ready*: whether the status of an epic was set to 'Refinement ready' before the start of its planning phase.
- *status*: the current status of an epic. The default is 'draft'. The user can update the status to 'Work in progress' (i.e., item still needs to be refined), 'Refinement ready' (i.e., item is refined and ready to be implemented), 'Complete' (i.e., item has been completed) and 'Cancelled' (i.e., item has been cancelled).

Team data

We extracted the following variables for each development teams that worked on an epic:

- *historical performance*: a team's ratio of epics delivered on time divided by the total number of epics delivered by the team so far.
- *office address*: the official office address of a team as specified on the actual start date of an epic.
- *parallel epics*: the number of other epics that a team worked on simultaneously (during the current epic).
- *team deviation*: a team's relative standard deviation from the regular cycle time during the current epic.
- *team existence*: the number of years a team has existed in its current composition of team members.
- *team point*: the total number of story points delivered by a team so far.
- *team size*: the number of people in a team as measured on the actual start date of an epic.
- *team stability*: the ratio of team members that did not change during the current and previous epic.
- *team velocity* (per sprint): the number of story points delivered by a team in a sprint during the current epic.

If applicable, these variables were aggregated at epic-level by computing the the median across teams (the data was not normally distributed).

Individual data

We extracted and aggregated the following variables for individual team members that worked on an epic:

- *developer age (ING)*: the number of years a team member has been working at ING.
- *developer age (team)*: the number of years a team member has been part of his/her current team.
- *developer (seniority)*: the seniority level of a team member. ING employs the five-stage Dreyfus skill model [86] to evaluate expertise based on previous experience in the software industry. Developers with a Dreyfuss skill level of 3 and higher were marked as being senior.
- *developer workload (points)* (per sprint): the number of story points assigned to a developer in a sprint of the current epic.
- *developer workload (stories)* (per sprint): the number of user stories assigned to a developer in a sprint of the current epic.

If applicable, these variables were aggregated at epic-level by computing the median across team members (the data was not normally distributed).